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Appendix A. Passerine data

Figure 7 - Number of reported opportunistic passerine occurrences in the Écrins National Park between 1974 and 2021. Three passerines were excluded from the barplot: Common Raven (*Corvus corax*), Red-billed Chough (*Pyrrhonorax pyrrhonorax*), and Alpine Chough (*Pyrrhonorax graculus*) for a total of 102,513 occurrences. Low counts in 1974 (3) and 1975 (2) explain the near absence of bars for those years.

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Appendix B. OSO covariates

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The OSO data are raster data produced at 10m and 20m spatial resolution. These two outputs are provided because the Sentinel-2 spectral bands used in the production process are acquired at 10m (visible and near-infrared) and 20m (red-edge, near and medium infrared) (Inglada, 2018). The nomenclature includes 24 classes. We then apply the nearest neighbor strategy to adjust the values to a 5m resolution, aligning with the elevation data resolution used in this study (IGN, 2018). We present in Table 2 the percentage of coverage for each OSO class in the Écrins National Park. The percentage of coverage for a chosen class is computed as the number of spatial cells of this class over the total number of spatial cells, based on a 5m regular grid of the Écrins National Park domain.

Table 2 – OSO data nomenclature including percentage coverage at a 5m resolution Écrins National Park. Classes with a percentage of coverage greater than 1% are in bold for easier readability.

Number	Nomenclature	Percentage
1	Dense buildings	<0.1%
2	Sparse buildings	0.6%
3	Industrial and commercial areas	0.3%
4	Road surfaces	<0.1%
5	Rapeseed	<0.1%
6	Cereal with straw	0.1%
7	Protein crops	<0.1%
8	Soybean	<0.1%
9	Sunflower	<0.1%
10	Corn	0.1%
11	Rice	<0.1%
12	Tubers/roots	<0.1%
13	Meadows	2.1%
14	Orchards	<0.1%
15	Vineyards	<0.1%
16	Deciduous forests	3.7%
17	Coniferous forests	16.0%
18	Grasslands	40.1%
19	Woody heaths	5.3%
20	Mineral surfaces	27.7%
21	Beaches and dunes	0.1%
22	Glaciers or snow	2.8%
23	Water	1.1%
0	Other	<0.1%

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Some classes are nearly absent in the Écrins National Park. Hence, the first four classes: *Dense buildings*, *Sparse buildings*, *Industrial and commercial areas* and *Road surfaces* are gathered into the **Urban** terminology. The following classes: *Rapeseed*, *Cereal with straw*, *Legumes*, *Soybean*, *Sunflower*, *Corn*, *Rice*, *Tubers/roots*, *Orchards*, *Vineyards* are gathered into the **Crops** terminology. Due to their very low percentage of surface area, the classes *Beaches and dunes* and *Other* are excluded from the analysis.

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Hence, the land cover land used classification used in the article is composed of 10 classes and is summarized in Table 3.

Table 3 – OSO data nomenclature adjusted for the Écrins National Park, including percentage coverage at a 5m resolution in the Écrins National Park.

Nomenclature	Percentage
Urban	0.9%
Crops	0.3%
Meadows	2.1%
Deciduous forests	3.7%
Coniferous forests	16.0%
Grasslands	40.1%
Woody heaths	5.3%
Mineral surfaces	27.7%
Glaciers or snow	2.8%
Water	1.1%

989 Using a spatial grid with a resolution of 500m, we calculated the coverage percentage of
 990 these 10 classes in each spatial cell to construct the OSO covariates, which formed the basis of
 991 the Principal Component Analysis.

992 **References**

993 Inglada, J., Vincent, A., & Thierion, V. (2018). *Theia OSO Land Cover Map 2018 [Data set]*. Zenodo.
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Appendix C. PCA figures

Figure 8 - Correlation circles of axis 1 and 2 of the PCA.

Figure 9 - Contribution of each spatial covariate to the axis 1 (a) and 2 (b) of the PCA.

Figure 10 – Correlation circles of axis 3 and 4 of the PCA.

Figure 11 – Contribution of each spatial covariate to the axis 3 (a) and 4 (b) of the PCA.

Figure 12 - Correlation circles of axis 5 and 6 of the PCA.

Figure 13 - Contribution of each spatial covariate to the axis 5 (a) and 6 (b) of the PCA.

Figure 14 – Map of passerine occurrences in wetlands (red circles) on OSO land cover land used classification in the Écrins National Park . Each number correspond to a class described in Table 2. The occurrences mainly occur in urban wetlands in the valleys, especially around the Lake of Serre-Pençon.

Appendix D. Parameter models – Priors

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999 We will now describe each prior used, i.e., the structure of the model components before
1000 updating them with information from observation data to obtain their posterior distributions.
1001 Each of the parameters β_i or γ_i associated with the fixed covariate effects has a very weakly
1002 informative Gaussian prior distribution centered at zero and with a precision hyperparameter
1003 $\tau_\beta = 10^{-3}$. For each month m , the spatial field $W_i^{(m)}$ is *a priori* represented using a 2-dimensional
1004 Gaussian random field based on the SPDE approach, where the Matérn covariance function has
1005 a fixed shape parameter $\nu^{(m)} = 1$, while the effective range, $\rho_i^{(m)}$, and the standard deviation,
1006 $\sigma_i^{(m)}$, are endowed with so-called penalized complexity priors (PC priors, Simpson et al., 2017): *a*
1007 *priori*, the probability of having range less than $\rho_0^{(m)} = 1$ is set to $\alpha_\rho^{(m)} = 0.5$, and the probability
1008 of having standard deviation larger than $\sigma_0^{(m)} = 1$ is set to $\alpha_\sigma^{(m)} = 0.5$. Since the spatial field $W_i^{(m)}$
1009 is replicated month by month, a cyclic *AR*(1) correlation structure (Box et al., 2015) is applied
1010 such that the value of $W_i^{(m)}$ is informed by the values of $W_i^{(m-1)}$ and $W_i^{(m+1)}$, where $m-1 = 12$
1011 for $m = 1$ and $m+1 = 1$ for $m = 12$. Regarding each period p , the inter-annual random effects
1012 $f_i(p)$ have independent and identically distributed Gaussian prior distributions with a precision
1013 hyperparameter $\tau_f = 10^{-3}$.

1014 References

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1016 *Control*. 5th edition. Hoboken, New Jersey: John Wiley and Sons Inc. 712 pp. ISBN: 978-1-118-
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- 1018 Simpson D., Rue H., Riebler A., Martins T.G., Sørbye S.H. (2017). *Penalising Model Component*
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Appendix E. Temporal and spatial cross-validation scenarios

Table 4 – Table of temporal cross-validation scenarios. The total number of space-time cells with at least one occurrence in the target group of species is 32,486. For a given period of four years, half of the cells and their associated occurrences are removed corresponding to one cross-validation scenario.

Scenario	Period	Removed cells	Percentage
13	1994-1997	1782	5.5%
14	1998-2001	1274	3.9%
15	2002-2005	1512	4.7%
16	2006-2009	1525	4.7%
17	2010-2013	2670	8.2%
18	2014-2017	4477	13.8%
19	2018-2021	3001	9.2%

Table 5 – Table of spatial cross-validation scenarios. The total number of space-time cells with at least one occurrence in the target group of species is 32,486. For a given municipality, the cells and their associated occurrences are removed corresponding to one cross-validation scenario.

Scenario	Municipality	Removed cells	Percentage
20	Saint-Christophe-en-Oisans	4407	13.6%
21	Valjouffrey	2473	7.6%
22	La Chapelle-en-Valgaudémar	2700	8.3%
23	Orcières	2167	6.7%
24	Châteauroux-les-Alpes	1839	5.7%
25	L'Argentière-la-Bessée	1345	4.1%
26	La Grave	2656	8.2%

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Appendix F. Reliability plots

Figure 15 – Reliability plot stratified by iso-intensity. Each point represents observed vs. predicted occurrences within a class. Cells were ranked by intensity and grouped into ten classes of equal cumulative intensity per species.

Figure 16 – Reliability plot stratified by target-group records. Each point represents observed vs. predicted occurrences within a class. Cells were ranked by the number of target-group records and grouped into ten classes.

Appendix G. Habitat preferences

Table 6 – Mean estimated parameters for spatial covariates: interpreted PCA Axes 1 to 3. Significant parameters based on the 95% credible interval are in bold.

Species (Occurrences)	Elevation	Coniferous forests	Grasslands
<i>Acanthis flammea</i> (464)	0.03	0.1	0.39
<i>Acrocephalus palustris</i> (138)	-0.39	0.25	0.45
<i>Aegithalos caudatus</i> (1599)	-0.29	0.15	-0.29
<i>Alauda arvensis</i> (1068)	0.98	-0.54	0.73
<i>Anthus spinoletta</i> (1934)	1	-0.57	0.65
<i>Anthus trivialis</i> (1292)	-0.13	0.53	0.47
<i>Bombycilla garrulus</i> (146)	NA	NA	NA
<i>Carduelis carduelis</i> (1549)	-0.21	-0.12	0.24
<i>Carduelis citrinella</i> (730)	0.49	0.04	0.33
<i>Certhia brachydactyla</i> (449)	-0.62	0.07	-0.35
<i>Certhia familiaris</i> (984)	-0.09	0.71	-0.27
<i>Chloris chloris</i> (668)	-0.27	-0.24	0.07
<i>Cinclus cinclus</i> (1887)	-0.67	0.11	-0.05
<i>Coccothraustes coccothraustes</i> (486)	-0.18	-0.18	-0.11
<i>Corvus corone</i> (1745)	-0.21	-0.04	0.24
<i>Corvus corone cornix</i> (187)	-0.66	0.08	1.02
<i>Corvus monedula</i> (152)	-0.43	-0.05	-0.71
<i>Cyanistes caeruleus</i> (1892)	-0.27	0.01	-0.17
<i>Delichon urbicum</i> (734)	0.21	-0.13	-0.04
<i>Emberiza cia</i> (1548)	0.1	0.01	0.05
<i>Emberiza cirrus</i> (202)	-0.69	0.16	0.11
<i>Emberiza citrinella</i> (1734)	-0.21	-0.07	0.39
<i>Emberiza hortulana</i> (134)	0.02	0.24	0.91
<i>Erithacus rubecula</i> (3354)	-0.35	0.26	-0.18
<i>Ficedula hypoleuca</i> (273)	-0.55	0.13	0.05
<i>Fringilla coelebs</i> (5447)	-0.26	0.3	0.03
<i>Fringilla montifringilla</i> (551)	-0.22	-0.01	0.04
<i>Garrulus glandarius</i> (2201)	-0.37	0.31	-0.13
<i>Hirundo rustica</i> (642)	-0.38	-0.11	0.38
<i>Lanius collurio</i> (834)	-0.24	-0.14	0.35
<i>Linaria cannabina</i> (1369)	0.47	-0.31	0.55
<i>Lophophanes cristatus</i> (2160)	-0.16	0.63	-0.17
<i>Loxia curvirostra</i> (1890)	0.22	0.83	0.34
<i>Lullula arborea</i> (321)	-0.15	0.48	0.94
<i>Luscinia megarhynchos</i> (376)	-0.46	0.12	0.29
<i>Monticola saxatilis</i> (566)	1.16	-0.35	0.47
<i>Montifringilla nivalis</i> (999)	1.48	-1.13	0.44
<i>Motacilla alba</i> (1088)	-0.55	-0.22	0.22
<i>Motacilla cinerea</i> (697)	-0.37	-0.05	-0.08

<i>Motacilla flava</i> (144)	-0.24	-0.59	0.37
<i>Nucifraga caryocatactes</i> (2275)	0.39	0.49	0.02
<i>Oenanthe oenanthe</i> (2263)	0.94	-0.68	0.66
<i>Parus major</i> (3165)	-0.31	0	-0.16
<i>Passer domesticus</i> (947)	-0.45	-0.44	-0.09
<i>Passer montanus</i> (209)	-0.9	0.22	0.8
<i>Periparus ater</i> (3595)	-0.18	0.45	-0.21
<i>Petronia petronia</i> (197)	-0.48	-0.42	0.24
<i>Phoenicurus ochruros</i> (4183)	0.48	-0.43	0.11
<i>Phoenicurus phoenicurus</i> (668)	-0.36	-0.4	-0.11
<i>Phylloscopus bonelli</i> (1668)	-0.17	0.17	-0.28
<i>Phylloscopus collybita</i> (2944)	-0.27	0.3	-0.03
<i>Pica pica</i> (1061)	-0.32	-0.18	0.24
<i>Poecile montanus</i> (2433)	0.07	0.7	-0.01
<i>Poecile palustris</i> (774)	-0.35	0.09	-0.21
<i>Prunella collaris</i> (1775)	1.2	-0.78	0.05
<i>Prunella modularis</i> (1386)	0.2	0.29	0.24
<i>Ptyonoprogne rupestris</i> (1695)	0.26	-0.11	-0.12
<i>Pyrrhula pyrrhula</i> (1816)	-0.32	0.44	-0.29
<i>Regulus ignicapilla</i> (686)	-0.37	0.74	-0.33
<i>Regulus regulus</i> (1030)	-0.27	0.79	-0.22
<i>Saxicola rubetra</i> (944)	-0.2	-0.15	0.74
<i>Saxicola rubicola</i> (313)	-0.14	-0.13	0.75
<i>Serinus serinus</i> (736)	-0.46	-0.09	-0.01
<i>Sitta europaea</i> (1841)	-0.47	0.03	-0.51
<i>Spinus spinus</i> (848)	-0.07	0.18	0.17
<i>Sturnus vulgaris</i> (353)	-0.56	-0.29	0.46
<i>Sylvia atricapilla</i> (1904)	-0.46	0.13	-0.24
<i>Sylvia borin</i> (576)	-0.49	0.14	0.23
<i>Sylvia communis</i> (143)	-0.39	0.36	0.71
<i>Sylvia curruca</i> (753)	0.26	0.35	0.28
<i>Tichodroma muraria</i> (1318)	0.86	-0.27	-0.46
<i>Troglodytes troglodytes</i> (2903)	-0.27	0.47	0.01
<i>Turdus merula</i> (2938)	-0.39	0.18	-0.04
<i>Turdus philomelos</i> (1209)	-0.37	0.56	-0.06
<i>Turdus pilaris</i> (1270)	0.04	0.2	0.29
<i>Turdus torquatus</i> (1665)	0.51	0.64	0.36
<i>Turdus viscivorus</i> (2585)	-0.11	0.43	0.21

Table 7 – Mean estimated parameters for spatial covariates: interpreted PCA Axes 4 to 6. Significant parameters based on the 95% credible interval are in bold.

Species (Occurrences)	Urban wetlands	Woody Heaths	Deciduous forests
<i>Acanthis flammea</i> (464)	-0.26	-0.09	0.13
<i>Acrocephalus palustris</i> (138)	-0.24	-0.04	-0.25
<i>Aegithalos caudatus</i> (1599)	0	0.07	-0.2
<i>Alauda arvensis</i> (1068)	0.11	-0.34	-0.01
<i>Anthus spinoletta</i> (1934)	0.02	0.1	0.01
<i>Anthus trivialis</i> (1292)	-0.43	-0.37	0.14
<i>Bombycilla garrulus</i> (146)	NA	NA	NA
<i>Carduelis carduelis</i> (1549)	0.15	-0.01	-0.08
<i>Carduelis citrinella</i> (730)	-0.02	0.04	0.03
<i>Certhia brachydactyla</i> (449)	0.05	0.03	-0.22
<i>Certhia familiaris</i> (984)	-0.27	-0.56	0.08
<i>Chloris chloris</i> (668)	0.25	0	-0.16
<i>Cinclus cinclus</i> (1887)	0.14	0.04	-0.16
<i>Coccothraustes coccothraustes</i> (486)	0.15	0	-0.1
<i>Corvus corone</i> (1745)	-0.02	-0.02	-0.11
<i>Corvus corone cornix</i> (187)	-0.09	0.08	-0.41
<i>Corvus monedula</i> (152)	-0.1	0.67	-0.23
<i>Cyanistes caeruleus</i> (1892)	-0.06	0.05	-0.12
<i>Delichon urbicum</i> (734)	-0.02	0.26	0.04
<i>Emberiza cia</i> (1548)	-0.2	0.16	-0.05
<i>Emberiza cirius</i> (202)	-0.19	0	-0.06
<i>Emberiza citrinella</i> (1734)	-0.11	-0.18	-0.18
<i>Emberiza hortulana</i> (134)	-0.29	0.09	-0.1
<i>Erithacus rubecula</i> (3354)	-0.1	0.01	-0.01
<i>Ficedula hypoleuca</i> (273)	0.09	0.09	-0.13
<i>Fringilla coelebs</i> (5447)	-0.12	-0.1	0.07
<i>Fringilla montifringilla</i> (551)	-0.09	-0.02	-0.08
<i>Garrulus glandarius</i> (2201)	-0.16	-0.03	-0.06
<i>Hirundo rustica</i> (642)	0.27	-0.07	-0.14
<i>Lanius collurio</i> (834)	-0.14	-0.2	-0.14
<i>Linaria cannabina</i> (1369)	0.08	0.04	0.12
<i>Lophophanes cristatus</i> (2160)	-0.11	-0.15	0.24
<i>Loxia curvirostra</i> (1890)	-0.23	-0.46	0.51
<i>Lullula arborea</i> (321)	-0.21	-0.05	0.01
<i>Luscinia megarhynchos</i> (376)	-0.14	-0.05	-0.11
<i>Monticola saxatilis</i> (566)	-0.61	0.09	0.35
<i>Montifringilla nivalis</i> (999)	-0.18	-0.09	0.01
<i>Motacilla alba</i> (1088)	0.34	-0.02	-0.16
<i>Motacilla cinerea</i> (697)	0.25	0.07	-0.2
<i>Motacilla flava</i> (144)	0.83	-0.72	-0.02
<i>Nucifraga caryocatactes</i> (2275)	0.15	-0.01	0.13

<i>Oenanthe oenanthe</i> (2263)	-0.15	0.06	0.03
<i>Parus major</i> (3165)	-0.03	0.11	-0.17
<i>Passer domesticus</i> (947)	0.38	-0.3	-0.05
<i>Passer montanus</i> (209)	0.07	-0.27	0
<i>Periparus ater</i> (3595)	-0.23	-0.24	0.26
<i>Petronia petronia</i> (197)	0.1	-0.32	-0.33
<i>Phoenicurus ochruros</i> (4183)	-0.15	0.11	-0.04
<i>Phoenicurus phoenicurus</i> (668)	0.23	-0.01	-0.17
<i>Phylloscopus bonelli</i> (1668)	-0.06	0.14	-0.15
<i>Phylloscopus collybita</i> (2944)	0	0.1	-0.14
<i>Pica pica</i> (1061)	-0.02	-0.12	-0.12
<i>Poecile montanus</i> (2433)	-0.17	-0.37	0.19
<i>Poecile palustris</i> (774)	-0.05	0.05	-0.11
<i>Prunella collaris</i> (1775)	-0.08	0.18	0.09
<i>Prunella modularis</i> (1386)	-0.17	0.02	0.22
<i>Ptyonoprogne rupestris</i> (1695)	-0.07	0.32	-0.03
<i>Pyrrhula pyrrhula</i> (1816)	-0.1	-0.24	0.14
<i>Regulus ignicapilla</i> (686)	-0.56	-0.42	0.35
<i>Regulus regulus</i> (1030)	-0.22	-0.24	0.3
<i>Saxicola rubetra</i> (944)	-0.07	-0.17	-0.22
<i>Saxicola rubicola</i> (313)	-0.21	-0.1	-0.26
<i>Serinus serinus</i> (736)	0.14	0.11	-0.08
<i>Sitta europaea</i> (1841)	0	-0.08	-0.16
<i>Spinus spinus</i> (848)	0.09	0.04	0.13
<i>Sturnus vulgaris</i> (353)	0.32	-0.67	0.03
<i>Sylvia atricapilla</i> (1904)	0.01	0.16	-0.09
<i>Sylvia borin</i> (576)	0	0.06	-0.21
<i>Sylvia communis</i> (143)	-0.3	0.09	-0.1
<i>Sylvia curruca</i> (753)	-0.49	-0.03	0.2
<i>Tichodroma muraria</i> (1318)	-0.16	0.4	0.13
<i>Troglodytes troglodytes</i> (2903)	-0.23	-0.13	0.05
<i>Turdus merula</i> (2938)	-0.07	0.05	-0.05
<i>Turdus philomelos</i> (1209)	0.03	-0.26	0.05
<i>Turdus pilaris</i> (1270)	-0.23	-0.15	0.06
<i>Turdus torquatus</i> (1665)	-0.6	-0.3	0.41
<i>Turdus viscivorus</i> (2585)	-0.22	-0.19	0.08

Table 8 – Mean estimated parameters for spatio-temporal covariates: anomalies of maximum temperature and anomalies of precipitation. Significant parameters based on the 95% credible interval are in bold.

Species (Occurrences)	Anomalies of Tmax	Anomalies of Precipitation
<i>Acanthis flammea</i> (464)	-0.002	-0.0215
<i>Acrocephalus palustris</i> (138)	-0.0044	0.2126
<i>Aegithalos caudatus</i> (1599)	0.001	-0.0633
<i>Alauda arvensis</i> (1068)	0.003	0.1266
<i>Anthus spinoletta</i> (1934)	0.0026	0.0376
<i>Anthus trivialis</i> (1292)	0.0019	0.0237
<i>Bombycilla garrulus</i> (146)	NA	NA
<i>Carduelis carduelis</i> (1549)	6e-04	-0.0013
<i>Carduelis citrinella</i> (730)	-0.0019	-0.0407
<i>Certhia brachydactyla</i> (449)	-0.001	-0.0068
<i>Certhia familiaris</i> (984)	0.0012	-0.0321
<i>Chloris chloris</i> (668)	-0.0015	-0.0212
<i>Cinclus cinclus</i> (1887)	-5e-04	-0.0223
<i>Coccothraustes coccothraustes</i> (486)	-0.0031	-0.272
<i>Corvus corone</i> (1745)	-0.0016	-0.0549
<i>Corvus corone cornix</i> (187)	-0.0052	-0.0928
<i>Corvus monedula</i> (152)	-0.0061	-5e-04
<i>Cyanistes caeruleus</i> (1892)	1e-04	-0.0823
<i>Delichon urbicum</i> (734)	5e-04	0.1054
<i>Emberiza cia</i> (1548)	-5e-04	0.0086
<i>Emberiza cirius</i> (202)	0.0024	0.0605
<i>Emberiza citrinella</i> (1734)	-0.0012	-0.0128
<i>Emberiza hortulana</i> (134)	0.0097	0.2859
<i>Erithacus rubecula</i> (3354)	-0.0013	-0.0195
<i>Ficedula hypoleuca</i> (273)	-5e-04	0.0073
<i>Fringilla coelebs</i> (5447)	-0.0011	-0.0236
<i>Fringilla montifringilla</i> (551)	0.0031	-0.2194
<i>Garrulus glandarius</i> (2201)	2e-04	0.0014
<i>Hirundo rustica</i> (642)	0.0073	0.0208
<i>Lanius collurio</i> (834)	0.0065	0.2762
<i>Linaria cannabina</i> (1369)	-0.0021	0.0514
<i>Lophophanes cristatus</i> (2160)	-2e-04	-0.0279
<i>Loxia curvirostra</i> (1890)	0.0013	-0.0489
<i>Lullula arborea</i> (321)	3e-04	0.0426
<i>Luscinia megarhynchos</i> (376)	-0.0094	0.1224
<i>Monticola saxatilis</i> (566)	0.006	0.1575
<i>Montifringilla nivalis</i> (999)	0.0014	-0.1305
<i>Motacilla alba</i> (1088)	-0.0024	0.0163
<i>Motacilla cinerea</i> (697)	-0.0032	0.0632
<i>Motacilla flava</i> (144)	-0.0051	0.1618

<i>Nucifraga caryocatactes</i> (2275)	0	4e-04
<i>Oenanthe oenanthe</i> (2263)	-6e-04	0.129
<i>Parus major</i> (3165)	2e-04	-0.0695
<i>Passer domesticus</i> (947)	-0.001	-0.0128
<i>Passer montanus</i> (209)	-0.0014	-0.0342
<i>Periparus ater</i> (3595)	4e-04	-0.0424
<i>Petronia petronia</i> (197)	-0.0036	0.0778
<i>Phoenicurus ochruros</i> (4183)	-1e-04	0.0478
<i>Phoenicurus phoenicurus</i> (668)	0.0071	0.1904
<i>Phylloscopus bonelli</i> (1668)	-4e-04	0.0714
<i>Phylloscopus collybita</i> (2944)	-0.0031	0.0105
<i>Pica pica</i> (1061)	0.0026	-0.0426
<i>Poecile montanus</i> (2433)	0.0013	-0.0437
<i>Poecile palustris</i> (774)	0.0036	-0.1009
<i>Prunella collaris</i> (1775)	0.0014	-0.0971
<i>Prunella modularis</i> (1386)	-0.0047	-0.0339
<i>Ptyonoprogne rupestris</i> (1695)	0.001	0.0746
<i>Pyrrhula pyrrhula</i> (1816)	9e-04	-0.0381
<i>Regulus ignicapilla</i> (686)	-0.004	-0.0081
<i>Regulus regulus</i> (1030)	0.002	-0.0646
<i>Saxicola rubetra</i> (944)	0.0027	0.2046
<i>Saxicola rubicola</i> (313)	0.0021	0.1124
<i>Serinus serinus</i> (736)	-7e-04	0.1231
<i>Sitta europaea</i> (1841)	-0.0027	-0.0289
<i>Spinus spinus</i> (848)	1e-04	-0.1358
<i>Sturnus vulgaris</i> (353)	0.005	0.0386
<i>Sylvia atricapilla</i> (1904)	-0.0034	0.0182
<i>Sylvia borin</i> (576)	-0.0041	0.1405
<i>Sylvia communis</i> (143)	0.0193	0.2733
<i>Sylvia curruca</i> (753)	0.0049	0.1386
<i>Tichodroma muraria</i> (1318)	-0.0019	-0.0576
<i>Troglodytes troglodytes</i> (2903)	-1e-04	0.0162
<i>Turdus merula</i> (2938)	6e-04	-0.0262
<i>Turdus philomelos</i> (1209)	-5e-04	-0.0198
<i>Turdus pilaris</i> (1270)	-0.0012	-0.1565
<i>Turdus torquatus</i> (1665)	-8e-04	-0.0144
<i>Turdus viscivorus</i> (2585)	0.0014	-0.0779

Table 9 – List of species removed from the habitat preference clustering based on the estimated mean parameters associated with the six spatial covariates corresponding to the first six axes of the principal component analysis detailed in Appendix C (Lasgorceux et al., 2024c).

Species (Occurrences)	Reason
<i>Acanthis flammea</i> (464)	1 significant covariate
<i>Acrocephalus palustris</i> (138)	2 significant covariates
<i>Bombycilla garrulus</i> (146)	131 occurrences in 2005
<i>Carduelis citrinella</i> (730)	2 significant covariates
<i>Cinclus cinclus</i> (1887)	Poor AUCs
<i>Corvus monedula</i> (152)	1 significant covariate
<i>Emberiza cirrus</i> (202)	1 significant covariate
<i>Emberiza hortulana</i> (134)	1 significant covariate
<i>Ficedula hypoleuca</i> (273)	2 significant covariates
<i>Fringilla montifringilla</i> (551)	1 significant covariate
<i>Luscinia megarhynchos</i> (376)	1 significant covariate
<i>Motacilla cinerea</i> (697)	Poor AUCs
<i>Passer montanus</i> (209)	2 significant covariates
<i>Sylvia communis</i> (143)	2 significant covariates

Figure 17 – a) Map of elevation in the Écrins National Park on a 500m × 500m regular grid. b) Map of clusters with the highest occurrences on a 500m × 500m regular grid. The highest number of occurrences is computed from the 63 classified species, excluding those with fewer than 100 occurrences and species listed in Table 9. Cluster 1 is associated with forest species, Cluster 2 with high-elevation species, and Cluster 3 with species found in the valleys.

Appendix H. Functional Principal Component Analysis

Figure 18 – Figure 18a displays the mean component of the spatial means of the month-dependent spatio-temporal Gaussian field W_i^m . Figure 18b shows the first two harmonics from the Functional Principal Component Analysis (FPCA) of the spatial means of the month-dependent spatio-temporal Gaussian field W_i^m . The black curve represents the first harmonic, explaining 61% of the variance in intra-annual variations. The red dotted curve represents the second harmonic, explaining 22% of the variance in intra-annual variations.

Table 10 – Scores associated with harmonics from FPCA. The first harmonic is linked to species overrepresented in winter, while the second pertains to species overrepresented in spring and summer. Species are categorized based on their primary migratory status within the territory of the Écrins National Park, as provided by park experts.

Species (Occurrences)	Winter	Summer	Migratory status
<i>Acanthis flammea</i> (464)	2.65	0.3	Resident
<i>Acrocephalus palustris</i> (138)	0.77	-0.57	Breeding migratory
<i>Aegithalos caudatus</i> (1599)	2.02	-1.13	Resident
<i>Alauda arvensis</i> (1068)	-4.67	-2.61	Breeding migratory
<i>Anthus spinoletta</i> (1934)	0.22	0.55	Breeding migratory
<i>Anthus trivialis</i> (1292)	-9.92	0.19	Breeding migratory
<i>Bombycilla garrulus</i> (146)	NA	NA	Wintering
<i>Carduelis carduelis</i> (1549)	1.15	-0.57	Resident
<i>Carduelis citrinella</i> (730)	1.63	-0.38	Resident
<i>Certhia brachydactyla</i> (449)	0.99	-0.56	Resident
<i>Certhia familiaris</i> (984)	0.94	-0.63	Resident
<i>Chloris chloris</i> (668)	1.3	-0.41	Resident
<i>Cinclus cinclus</i> (1887)	NA	NA	Resident
<i>Coccothraustes coccothraustes</i> (486)	0.85	-3.22	Resident
<i>Corvus corone</i> (1745)	1.04	-0.6	Resident
<i>Corvus corone cornix</i> (187)	1.78	-0.23	Resident
<i>Corvus monedula</i> (152)	0.72	-0.75	Resident
<i>Cyanistes caeruleus</i> (1892)	1.46	-0.76	Resident
<i>Delichon urbicum</i> (734)	-3.29	2.17	Breeding migratory
<i>Emberiza cia</i> (1548)	1.04	0.11	Resident
<i>Emberiza cirius</i> (202)	1.78	-0.08	Resident
<i>Emberiza citrinella</i> (1734)	0.42	0.91	Breeding migratory
<i>Emberiza hortulana</i> (134)	1.88	1.29	Breeding migratory
<i>Erithacus rubecula</i> (3354)	0.72	0.41	Resident
<i>Ficedula hypoleuca</i> (273)	-3.13	9.91	Breeding migratory
<i>Fringilla coelebs</i> (5447)	1.02	0.2	Resident
<i>Fringilla montifringilla</i> (551)	2.12	-1.67	Wintering
<i>Garrulus glandarius</i> (2201)	1.2	-0.41	Resident
<i>Hirundo rustica</i> (642)	-1.74	5.23	Breeding migratory
<i>Lanius collurio</i> (834)	2.03	1.75	Breeding migratory
<i>Linaria cannabina</i> (1369)	1.08	-0.43	Resident
<i>Lophophanes cristatus</i> (2160)	1.28	-1.79	Resident
<i>Loxia curvirostra</i> (1890)	1.71	-0.89	Resident
<i>Lullula arborea</i> (321)	-0.86	-1.1	Breeding migratory
<i>Luscinia megarhynchos</i> (376)	-13.95	-2.51	Breeding migratory
<i>Monticola saxatilis</i> (566)	0.08	1.21	Breeding migratory
<i>Montifringilla nivalis</i> (999)	1.4	-0.73	Resident
<i>Motacilla alba</i> (1088)	1.04	1.56	Breeding migratory
<i>Motacilla cinerea</i> (697)	NA	NA	Resident

<i>Motacilla flava</i> (144)	-3.02	0.21	Breeding migratory
<i>Nucifraga caryocatactes</i> (2275)	-2.61	-3.66	Resident
<i>Oenanthe oenanthe</i> (2263)	-6.52	-1.11	Breeding migratory
<i>Parus major</i> (3165)	1	-0.63	Resident
<i>Passer domesticus</i> (947)	1.47	-0.36	Resident
<i>Passer montanus</i> (209)	1.18	-0.57	Resident
<i>Periparus ater</i> (3595)	0.96	-0.66	Resident
<i>Petronia petronia</i> (197)	0.84	-0.64	Resident
<i>Phoenicurus ochruros</i> (4183)	0.62	0.91	Breeding migratory
<i>Phoenicurus phoenicurus</i> (668)	1.66	0.86	Breeding migratory
<i>Phylloscopus bonelli</i> (1668)	-13.44	-1.74	Breeding migratory
<i>Phylloscopus collybita</i> (2944)	-0.82	3.58	Breeding migratory
<i>Pica pica</i> (1061)	1.52	-0.48	Resident
<i>Poecile montanus</i> (2433)	1.36	-0.67	Resident
<i>Poecile palustris</i> (774)	1.04	-0.59	Resident
<i>Prunella collaris</i> (1775)	1.21	-0.73	Resident
<i>Prunella modularis</i> (1386)	0.05	1.54	Resident
<i>Ptyonoprogne rupestris</i> (1695)	-0.63	1.47	Breeding migratory
<i>Pyrrhula pyrrhula</i> (1816)	1.49	-0.88	Resident
<i>Regulus ignicapilla</i> (686)	0.68	0.53	Breeding migratory
<i>Regulus regulus</i> (1030)	1.42	-0.87	Resident
<i>Saxicola rubetra</i> (944)	1.7	1.26	Breeding migratory
<i>Saxicola rubicola</i> (313)	1.6	0.25	Breeding migratory
<i>Serinus serinus</i> (736)	1.07	0.13	Breeding migratory
<i>Sitta europaea</i> (1841)	1.71	-1.13	Resident
<i>Spinus spinus</i> (848)	1.99	-1.15	Resident
<i>Sturnus vulgaris</i> (353)	-1.41	-2.53	Resident
<i>Sylvia atricapilla</i> (1904)	-0.15	2.25	Breeding migratory
<i>Sylvia borin</i> (576)	0.35	1.86	Breeding migratory
<i>Sylvia communis</i> (143)	1.41	0.58	Breeding migratory
<i>Sylvia curruca</i> (753)	-4.8	2.74	Breeding migratory
<i>Tichodroma muraria</i> (1318)	1.63	-0.52	Resident
<i>Troglodytes troglodytes</i> (2903)	1.08	-0.38	Resident
<i>Turdus merula</i> (2938)	0.94	-0.59	Resident
<i>Turdus philomelos</i> (1209)	0.28	1.46	Resident
<i>Turdus pilaris</i> (1270)	2.11	-2.43	Resident
<i>Turdus torquatus</i> (1665)	1.34	-0.43	Breeding migratory
<i>Turdus viscivorus</i> (2585)	0.94	-0.63	Resident

Appendix I. Comparison trend with other datasets

Table 11 – Contingency tables on significant trends. Column 1 presents a MHB vs Écrins National Park (ENP) data comparison (23 species). Column 2 presents STOC vs ENP data comparison (12 species). The tables are ordered according to the primary habitat category assigned in the MHB and STOC classifications, respectively. Correlation numbers report the correlation between corrected trends (see ‘Materials and Methods – Model evaluation and post-processing – Inter-annual effects’ subsection).

(a) Alpine habitat (4 species). Correlation = 0.42.

	MHB negative	MHB positive
ENP negative	4	0
ENP positive	0	0

(b) Alpine habitat (0 species) – not studied by the STOC.

	STOC negative	STOC positive
ENP negative	0	0
ENP positive	0	0

(c) Forest species (12 species). Correlation= 0.40.

	MHB negative	MHB positive
ENP negative	2	4
ENP positive	1	5

(d) Forest species (5 species). Correlation=0.85.

	STOC negative	STOC positive
ENP negative	2	0
ENP positive	1	2

(e) Farmland habitat (4 species). Correlation = –0.88. Removed *Emberiza hortulana* from the correlation since the species does not breed in Switzerland anymore.

	MHB negative	MHB positive
ENP negative	3	1
ENP positive	0	0

(f) Farmland habitat (1 species: *Emberiza hortulana*).

	STOC negative	STOC positive
ENP negative	1	0
ENP positive	0	0

(g) Settlements habitat (1 species: *Passer domesticus*).

	MHB negative	MHB positive
ENP negative	1	0
ENP positive	0	0

(h) Settlements habitat (1 species: *Chloris chloris*).

	STOC negative	STOC positive
ENP negative	0	0
ENP positive	0	1

(i) Generalist species (2 species). Correlation= 1.

	MHB negative	MHB positive
ENP negative	1	0
ENP positive	1	0

(j) Generalist species (5 species). Correlation= 0.85.

	STOC negative	STOC positive
ENP negative	0	4
ENP positive	0	1

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Appendix J. Mean elevation of *Phoenicurus ochrurus* occurrences

Figure 19 – Distribution and mean elevation of *Phoenicurus ochrurus* occurrences in the ENP. (a) Mean elevation of occurrences by 15-day periods between 2017 and 2021. Occurrences in January, February, and December were removed as the means were computed from fewer than 2 occurrences and introduced artefacts; the 15-day periods therefore start from early March (period 5) and end at the end of November (period 22). The summer period for *Phoenicurus ochrurus* was defined as May to October inclusive based on this figure. Data were restricted to 5 years to limit the confounding effects of inter-annual phenological shifts and the species’ annual biological cycle. (b) Number of *Phoenicurus ochrurus* occurrences per month over the period 1994–2021. (c) Mean elevation of *Phoenicurus ochrurus* occurrences in the Écrins National Park over 1994–2021.